

Flee the Tribe

By Ramin Saadat

My grandfather was a farmer and a wise man. Though illiterate, never having read or written a single word in his life, he knew a great deal about the world and about people.

I still remember clearly that when I was very small I once asked him why, in our culture, close relatives marry one another, whereas in some parts of the world this is considered wrong.

He said it was originally a matter of keeping inheritance undivided and preserving the family's wealth, itself a response to an even older human custom.

He then explained that long ago people lived in scattered villages and tribes, and had gradually come to realise that when close kin marry, the number of weak and sickly individuals in the tribe slowly increases. That is why they always sought partners from another tribe, from among strangers, so that fresh blood might enter the group. (Neither he nor I had heard anything of genes or heredity at that time.)

The example he offered came from his own farming world. He said you cannot sow the same seed in the same field year after year; you must rotate both fields and seeds each time, so that -as he put it- the land does not lose its breath, and the seed does not grow old and spent.

He believed the same was true of people: they had to marry strangers for a healthy generation to come into being. That was why, when wars broke out, people carried off individuals from other tribes, or seized upon any pretext to bring girls or boys from other villages, so that the lineage might continue well, and what he called "fresh blood" would flow into the veins of society.

He said that in his childhood, if a strong, healthy-looking traveller passed near the tribe or village, they would bring him home and treat him with great generosity and warmth, hoping he would agree to stay and marry one of the tribe's daughters, thus securing that "fresh blood". May his soul rest in peace; he was a truly wise man.

Later, when I was older, I read that among chimpanzees and bonobos the very same behaviour exists: when a female reaches maturity she leaves her own group and migrates to join another. Apparently they too, unknowingly, observe this matter of "fresh blood" for their group. Perhaps this behaviour is an evolved trait for introducing fresh genes, a behaviour beneficial for genetic mixing and diversity, one that arose through evolution and has persisted because it proved advantageous for both the individual and the genes.

The same is seen in certain birds, such as sparrows, where females migrate to other groups, and among lions, where it is the young males that leave the pride.

I have said all this in order to arrive at our world today.

We no longer live in scattered tribes or mud-walled villages. On the contrary, several million people now live and work side by side in a single great city. A single tall building may contain dozens or hundreds of families. Yet in my view the matter of "tribes" still exists today, only in a different form, no longer in thatched huts or mud houses.

What I mean is our permanent life and presence inside social networks.

Today, on social media, we live in different tribes: Telegram groups, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, X and other platforms...

True, we share no blood or genetic ties with these virtual friends, our fellow tribespeople, yet our attachment and connection closely resemble genetic kinship, only carried through memes.

Memes are the news items, jokes, short video clips, photographs of endearing cats, jibes at politicians and the like, the things we post to one another and receive back as laughing emojis, likes and comments.

Memes are created somewhere, travel through social networks, spread, and race from one end of the world to the other with extraordinary speed. We are connected to one another through these shared memes, and it is they that create friendship and fellow-feeling between us, just as shared genes connect the members of a family, a pack, or a tribe.

Memes, of course, are not confined to today's world and social media; they have existed throughout human societies. Some are beneficial, some neutral, some even parasitic, hitching a ride alongside beneficial memes, much as genes do. Some genes are advantageous (such as those conferring resistance to disease or skills for survival); some are harmful (such as those that cause sickle-cell anaemia or hereditary heart conditions); and some are parasitic, replicating and transmitting themselves alongside beneficial genes, as transposons, or "jumping genes", do, simply exploiting the body's machinery.

To be more precise: historical examples of memes include flags, inscriptions carved in stone, folk and ethnic dress, proverbs, poems, even the form of buildings and architecture. The most familiar are perhaps the cross of Jesus Christ, the crescent moon among Muslims, and the hammer and sickle on the red flag of nineteenth- and twentieth-century communism.

All of these were memes throughout history, gradually multiplying and spreading across the world, though far more slowly than today's dancing-cat videos or digital emojis.

Today, too, we are connected to our "fellow tribespeople" on various social-media platforms through shared memes. We love one another, we miss one another. If a few days pass without someone posting, or without a like or comment from them, even if we do not message them directly we still find ourselves thinking: Where are they? What has happened? Has something gone wrong? It is just as in a real tribe, where if someone did not emerge from their hut or tent for several days, we would wonder whether they were ill, whether we ought to go and ask after them.

So far there is nothing wrong with this, it is, in fact, rather fine and admirable that we all behave like a tribe, keeping in touch and asking after one another. But this is not the whole story. If you would like to know, I will explain why this way of living virtually inside internet tribes and online social networks, for all its merits, is also harmful and even dangerous.

Perhaps the most serious problem is that we live inside an "informational and memetic bubble". The reality is that social-media platforms are built on the principle of showing us only what we already like and approve of. This feature places each of us inside a bubble -or echo chamber- where we hear only our own voice and the voices of those who think exactly as we do within our own tribe.

This "design feature" of the platforms means that we remain effectively and entirely unaware of the data, evidence, news and arguments of those who are not of our tribe. We do not know what is really happening in the actual world, just like someone who has never left their own village.

This one-sidedness makes our perceptions, judgements and decisions about the world skewed. And because our predictions fail to come true, we grow despondent and angry.

We look upon people in other virtual tribes as fools, pity them, and are even enraged by them, even when those people are our spouse, our brother or sister, or our cousins. This is precisely the opposite

of the biological reality in which we were meant to love those who share our genes (our biological tribespeople) and make sacrifices for them.

Take Britain, where I live. Imagine I follow the Green Party on social media, and my friends (my memetic, virtual tribespeople) are all environmental activists. My feed fills with posts and memes about global warming, species extinction, and the urgent need for a carbon tax. I become so absorbed in this tribe that I assume the whole of Britain shares these concerns. Yet at that very same moment, in another tribe behind an algorithmic wall, supporters of Nigel Farage or Reform UK see none of this. They live inside their own bubble, reading, writing and posting only about border control, immigration and the national economy.

When election day arrives, I am shocked by the results, just like someone who has spent their whole life in a small village and is suddenly cast into a great city. I ask myself: "How can anyone vote for them?"

The answer is simple: I had never encountered their "intellectual genes", because I had spent my whole life inside my own tribe.

The same happens in America. On one side stands a tribe that venerates the right to bear arms as a sacred tribal inheritance; on the other, a tribe that sees gun control as the only salvation. The algorithms never permit the reasoned arguments of the opposing side to reach you, because they know that if you encounter something you dislike, you might close the application. They keep us imprisoned in our tribes so that they may profit.

In the debates over abortion or the Muslim community in Britain, the pattern is the same: we live on separate islands with no bridge between them, and only our own "ideological blood" flows through our veins.

When social media first appeared, many years ago, everyone was delighted. "How wonderful!" they said. "Now all the people of the

world will live in a global village. Geographical and political borders will dissolve; the way will be opened for cultural exchange and friendship between the civilisations of East and West, North and South..." Today we see that, unhappily, not only has none of that come to pass, within nations too we have grown further apart, each of us imprisoned in our own tribe.

Today we can no longer even tolerate hearing the opinion of an old friend, a sister, or a father, because we regard them as belonging to another tribe, and another tribe means the enemy.

Yes, the truth is that after thousands upon thousands of years of tribal life throughout history, it has become deeply embedded in the nature of our minds and beliefs that the inhabitants of other tribes may be dangerous, and that we must always approach them with caution. This same tribal instinct tells us that if we come to agree with people from other tribes, listen to what they say, or befriend them, we have "betrayed our own tribe". And betrayal of one's own group is counted among the gravest offences and sins in every culture.

It is no coincidence that the theme and story of so many of the greatest literary works in human history, and so many of the tales told to us since childhood, concern precisely this matter of "betrayal": treacherous collaboration with the enemy against one's own tribe.

We see this theme everywhere in history: from Enkidu in the Epic of Gilgamesh, who turned his back on the "tribe of the wild" to join civilisation, to Judas, who betrayed his circle of companions with a kiss; from the wandering of Siavash between the two tribes of Iran and Turan in the ancient Persian epics, to the tragedies of Shakespeare, all give voice to an eternal fear: the fear that the boundary between "us" and "them" will be broken, and that someone from the tribe will betray "us".

Perhaps this same fear lies coiled and hidden in all our minds, which is why today, too, we cling with all our strength to the

opinions and memes of our virtual tribes and resist any doubt about these "insider" ideas and beliefs, even when all the evidence cries out that our view is wrong. No, we will not change our thinking, because we do not wish to betray our tribe. No, we are not traitors!

The consequence of this behaviour is that we effectively hand the elders of our own tribe a blank cheque: we give them permission to say or do whatever they wish, and we accept it all wholesale, whatever it may be. After all, have we not handed them that blank cheque to write whatever they please?

We must remember that in these digital tribes, no "fresh blood" of opposing argument ever enters. We do not develop immunity to other people's ideas; instead, each day we grow more fearful, weaker, more fragile and angrier. Just as the female chimpanzee would weaken her group's future if she remained in her birth group, so too, if we never leave our virtual tribes and never hear a dissenting voice, we suffer a kind of collective intellectual stunting.

We think the whole world is exactly what appears on the screen of our telephone, when in reality we are merely looking at our tribe's family album, the same faded photographs, the same memories we have heard a thousand times repeated. It is thus that today we are ignorant of the rest of the world, of the conversations flowing through other tribes, and of the great storms that have risen across the globe.

That is why we cannot bear to hear the arguments of anyone from the neighbouring tribe. When we hear the words of "others" we grow angry, mutter curses under our breath at the inhabitants of other tribes, flee from them, and take refuge in our own. Why? Because within our own tribe, under our own wooden-and-reed shelter, or beneath the warm quilt of our scant and repetitive certainties, we feel at peace. And above all, we are not forced to betray the tribe. What could be finer than that?

You ask what is to be done? In my view, perhaps the wisest course is to belong to several tribes at once. We must drive from our minds

the idea that listening to others is an act of betrayal. We should come to understand that total attachment and absolute loyalty to our own tribe is, before anything else, a betrayal of ourselves, a betrayal of our own human intelligence, of the critical reason and understanding that nature has placed within us.

For this reason, it would be good to visit others in different tribes from time to time, to ask after them and sit and listen to what they have to say.

It would be good to belong simultaneously to several intellectually diverse groups and to hear their news and viewpoints. This keeps our minds open and alert, sharpens our powers of critical analysis, and ensures that we "never again sign a blank cheque for anyone".

Yes, today's world very much resembles my grandfather's small garden. Had he wished to keep his garden green and abundant using only the seeds he had gathered himself over the years, after a time the flowers would have grown smaller, the colours would have faded, and the plants would have collapsed at the first blight. He used to say: "These seeds have no life left in them, they have only married themselves and remained inside themselves."

Perhaps if he were alive today he would say: Life needs fresh blood, and that blood is scattered freely through the open air. Go and meet people, laugh with them, learn from them. Go and listen and read, so that you may know more and grow larger... You should live free and unconfined, like the breeze and the wind, free from all tribal attachments...

I don't know. He was a very wise and great man. Perhaps he would simply say:

My dear child, never consider yourself a member of any tribe, and never sign a blank cheque for anyone. Wherever you see wrongdoing, injustice, dishonesty or falsehood, stand firm against it and do not stay silent. If you see your tribe demanding blind obedience, know that this is no longer your place. Leave your

tribe... You can be like the breeze and the wind, free and unbound,
and soar high above all tribes, great and small, in the open sky!

Flee your tribe, my child. Flee...
